

HIGHER EDUCATION AS A PEDAGOGICAL SYSTEM FOR ENSURING SOCIETAL DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. This thesis presents views on the role of higher education in the development of society, its importance in the development of human capital, and its characteristics as a pedagogical system.

Keywords: higher education, human capital, formation of an innovative economy, modern pedagogical system, conceptual model, pedagogical factors, labor market, social development.

The economic, social, spiritual and cultural development of modern society is directly related to the quality of human capital, and the higher education system occupies a leading position in the formation of human capital. Therefore, the scientific study of higher education as a pedagogical system that ensures the development of society, the improvement of its theoretical and methodological foundations and the development of mechanisms for its development are of great scientific and practical importance. The main goal is to systematically study the pedagogical, social and innovative functions of higher education in ensuring the development of society, to identify the factors determining its effectiveness and to develop a pedagogical model that meets the requirements of modern development.

The study provides an in-depth analysis of the main areas of higher education that affect the development of society, including the quality of personnel training, innovative activities, scientific and research work, spiritual and educational education, the development of digital competencies and social cooperation.

Also, the degree of adaptation of higher education to the needs of modern society, its role in economic development, civil society and the development of human capital will be determined. As a result of the research, scientifically based recommendations will be developed to expand the pedagogical capabilities of higher education in ensuring social development. Based on the purpose of the research, the following tasks are envisaged:

1. Analysis of theoretical views on the role of higher education in social development: determination of the content and essence of the concepts of higher education and social development, study of scientific views on the development of higher education in the disciplines of pedagogy, sociology, philosophy and

economics, systematization of the functions of higher education in ensuring social development, substantiation of the importance of higher education as a social institution;

2. Identifying the structural components that characterize higher education as a pedagogical system: analyzing the components of the goal, content, method, means and result of the higher education system, studying the relationships between the subjects and objects of the pedagogical system, analyzing the management and monitoring mechanisms of higher education, determining the impact of modern pedagogical technologies on the effectiveness of higher education;

3. Assessing the impact of the higher education system of Uzbekistan on the development of society: studying the contribution of higher education institutions to economic development, determining the relationship between the quality of personnel training and the needs of the labor market, analyzing the role of higher education in the development of civil society institutions, assessing its importance in the formation of spiritual, educational and civic competencies of young people;

4. Study and comparative analysis of foreign experiences: study of advanced experiences of higher education systems of developed countries, analysis of innovative development models of universities and their impact on social development, study of the activities of universities that occupy high places in international rankings, identification of opportunities for applying foreign experiences in the conditions of Uzbekistan;

5. Identification of innovative and digital development factors of higher education: study of the pedagogical effectiveness of digital educational technologies, assessment of the impact of artificial intelligence and digital platforms on the quality of education, development of mechanisms for forming an innovative educational environment, development of scientific recommendations on the digital transformation of higher education.

6. Investigating the link between higher education and human capital development: analyzing the relationship between human capital theory and higher education; determining the connection between the quality of education and economic growth; examining the link between graduates' professional competencies and their success in the labor market; and substantiating the role of higher education in the development of an innovation-driven economy.

7. Developing a pedagogical model for higher education that fosters societal progress: creating a conceptual model aligned with modern trends in higher

education development; defining the model's components and their interrelationships; establishing criteria for the model's effectiveness; and preparing methodological recommendations for the model's practical implementation.

8. Organizing and evaluating the effectiveness of experimental trials: testing the developed pedagogical model in higher education institutions; statistically analyzing the results; determining the model's effectiveness; and formulating practical recommendations and methodological guidelines.

Reforming the education system, strengthening its role in the development of society and developing it on the basis of international standards were recognized as one of the priority areas of state policy. Therefore, a number of scientific studies were conducted on the role of higher education in the development of society, its importance in the development of human capital, and its characteristics as a pedagogical system.

Among the scientists, R.H. Jo'rayev, N.K. Saidahmedov, B.Kh. Khodjaev, U.N. Nishonaliyev, A. Abdukodirov, M. Kuronov, Sh. Sharipov, O. Muslimov, N. Egamberdiyeva and other researchers studied the issues of modernization of higher education, competency-based approach, innovative pedagogy, quality management of education, and improvement of the personnel training system. Theodore Schultz also studied the relationship between education and economic development and substantiated the strategic importance of higher education in the development of society. In the field of pedagogy and sociology of education, scholars such as Philip G. Altbach, Burton R. Clark, Martin Trow, Jamil Salmi, and others have studied the role of higher education in the processes of globalization, massification, and innovative development.

However, the analysis of the conducted research shows that the essence of higher education as a holistic pedagogical system ensuring the development of society, its structural components, development mechanisms, indicators of social effectiveness and the development of a pedagogical model have not been sufficiently carried out.

In conclusion, we can say that although in our country individual aspects of higher education - the quality of education, the competency-based approach, innovative activities and management issues - have been studied, its theoretical and conceptual model as a pedagogical system ensuring the development of society has not yet been fully developed. Abroad, this issue has been widely studied, and there is a need to adapt their best practices to the conditions of the national education system.

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